

FEEDSTOCK AND PROCESSING EFFECTS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF NATURAL FIBER THERMOSET COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Natural fibre composites are seen as an attractive alternative to glass-fibre composites in a variety of applications due to their reduced cost, low density, and environmental benefits. Over the past decade, there has been significant research on the mechanical behaviour of various natural fibre systems, but there has been relatively few studies comparing the effect of feedstock and processing variables in the same experimental set. In this comprehensive study, the mechanical performance of various natural fibre thermoset composites is compared. The effect of fibre type, fibre processing and composite fabrication method were investigated. Mechanical testing results include tensile strength, tensile modulus, elongation and charpy impact. Results were compared to conventional glass-fibre composites as a baseline.

Overall, the following conclusions were found. Random mat glass fibre composites were shown to have significantly higher strength, elongation and impact toughness relative to all natural fibre composites tested, while modulus values were more comparable. Compression molded (CM) laminates were found to perform better than those manufactured using hand lay-up (HL). This was predominantly due to better consolidation resulting in higher fibre volume fractions and lower air void content. The performance of resin transfer molded (RTM) versus compression molded (CM) laminates were found to depend on fibre type (glass versus natural). There was no appreciable differences in laminate properties between the different natural fibres samples tested (i.e. natural fibre type, length and non-woven mat manufacturing method did not show significant effects). This suggests that improvements in natural fibre processing and mat manufacturing methods will be required to achieve composites which perform as well as synthetic counterparts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite parts and structures made from glass fibres represent a significant market worldwide. In North America alone, the demand for glass fibres currently exceeds 600,000 tons per year [1]. The use of glass fibres in reinforced thermosetting plastics is a significant portion of this demand.

Natural fibres have an enormous potential in supplementing or replacing glass fibres in composite applications. The advantage of natural fibre systems is their low weight and cost relative to glass fibre systems. In addition, natural fibres are more environmentally benign compared to synthetic glass fibres. While significant work has been conducted to date on the application of natural fibres in automotive [2] and construction applications (e.g. decking materials) [3], very little work to date has been conducted on low-cost, low-end manufacturing applications such as open and close moulded consumer goods (e.g. tubs, boats) and FRP corrosion systems (tanks and piping).

Lay-up or infusion molding methods are a suite of processes that utilize dry woven or non-woven fibre mat reinforcement (preforms) in conjunction with a thermoset resin. These include common methods such as hand lay-up, compression molding (CM) and resin transfer molding (RTM). In the hand lay-up operation, components are created by directly applying resin to dry woven and non-woven

mats on top of an open mould. Consolidation is performed by manually operated roller systems, and the part is left to cure at room temperature. In compression molding (CM), dry woven and nonwoven mats are placed with liquid resin into a two part mold, and a hydraulic press is used to apply pressure and heat to cure the part. In resin transfer moulding (RTM), dry woven and nonwoven mats are placed in a closed mould which is then infused with a low viscosity resin. During the infusion process, the mould can be heated to decrease processing times, and can have an applied vacuum to improve part quality.

While these processes are relatively low-cost, low-technology methods, they are well established and are used extensively in operations worldwide. There is a significant potential to introduce natural fibre systems into these operations without significant a risk or cost proposition to the manufacturer.

In terms of the literature, there has been significant effort in developing and characterizing natural fibre reinforced thermoplastic resin composites [4-8] produced by extrusion/compounding methods. However, much less work has been conducted on developing natural fibre based thermoset composites using lay-up and infusion methods.

O'Dell [9] used the RTM technique to manufacture jute-fibre reinforced composites. Both untreated and glycol-treated jute non-woven fibre mats were used as the reinforcement in unsaturated polyester resin. The study demonstrated that no significant improvement was achieved by the fibre treatment. In addition, neither of the jute composites could achieve the strength and modulus of the glass-reinforced composites at the same volume fractions.

Sèbe et al [10] attempted to modify hemp fibres with methacrylic anhydride and pyridine to improve adhesion between the unsaturated polyester resin and cellulose chains of the fibres. The authors used the RTM technique to obtain natural fibre reinforced composites. Non-woven hemp and glass-fibre mats were used as reinforcement. The SEM analysis of the fracture surfaces of the hemp-reinforced composites demonstrated that the adhesion between the unsaturated polyester resin and the fibres was significantly improved. The improved adhesion, however, did not significantly contribute to improving of the overall mechanical properties of the composites.

Rouison et al [11] studied the curing behaviour of the unsaturated polyester resin in the presence of natural fibres. Non-woven mats made of 67% hemp and of 33% kenaf fibres were used as reinforcement. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) showed that the degree of curing does not exceed approximately 87% in the presence of natural fibres (this is unusually low for this type of resin; typical degree of curing reaches numbers close to 100% when using glass-fibre reinforcement). The authors attributed this low degree of curing to lower conductivity of the natural fibres compared to glass fibres. The authors also noticed that the resin injection time increased significantly with the fibre volume content. Therefore, the maximum of 20.6% fibre volume fraction was used to prevent premature resin curing.

Many existing manufacturers in automotive and aerospace industries traditionally use unsaturated polyester (UPE) resins of different formulations. Dansiri et al [12], however, synthesised a blend of two benzoxazine monomers to use as a novel resin for natural fibres in RTM applications. Such resin demonstrated slightly better mechanical properties than a traditional UPE formulation. In addition, lower water absorption characteristics of the benzoxazine-based resin were demonstrated. Carefully choosing the curing regime, resin formulation and fibre load fractions, they demonstrated that superior mechanical properties compared to the neat resin can be achieved.

The main objective of the current study is to evaluate the potential of utilizing natural fibres as a replacement to glass-fibre in low-cost thermoset composite applications. In particular, the effect of fibre type and manufacturing method on the resulting mechanical performance was investigated.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

A series of experiments were performed to test the properties of various composites produced from non-woven natural fibre mats using hand lay-up, compression molding (CM) and resin transfer molding (RTM) processes. Two commercially available thermoset resins were used in the study:

- Dion 490 resin (Reichhold Inc.): a synthetic polyester (terephthalic acid based) resin
- Envirez T-25 (Ashland): a bio-based (soy bean) polyester resin

Resin selection was dependent on manufacturing technique. The Dion 490 resin was used for hand lay-up, while the Envirez T-25 was used for both CM and RTM.

Three (3) types of fibres were utilized in this study including hemp bast (various lengths), flax (retted and whole straw) and glass-fibre (see Table 1). All natural fibres were supplied and processed at Alberta Innovates Technology Future's (AITF) lab facilities in Edmonton, Canada. The density of the fibres were determined using the Archimedes method (ASTM D3800-99), and is summarized in Table 2.

Fibre Type	Fibre Cut Length	Source
Hemp	10 mm	AITF (decorticated & cut)
Flax (retted/whole)	10 mm	AITF (decorticated & cut)
Hemp	25 mm	AITF (decorticated & cut)
Hemp	50 mm	Hemp Technology UK (decorticated); AITF (cut)

Table 1: Natural fibre types tested

Fibre	Density (kg/m ³)
E-Glass	2,550
Hemp	1,480
Flax	1,300

Table 2: Measured fibre densities

2.2 Fibre Mat Processing Methods

Both dry laid and wet laid non-woven mats from a number of sources were evaluated in this study. Composite test samples were manufactured using mats obtained from both commercial mat forming operations (dry and wet laid), and mats developed in-house at AITF (wet laid only). The dry laid mats were manufactured using the commercial Rando-Webber process. Random E-glass chopped strand mats, purchased commercially (Viking Plastics, Canada), were used as a reference.

A novel lab-scale mat forming system (based on the wet laid technique) was developed at AITF's facility in Edmonton, AB. This system is comprised of a large slurry tank and screening system which produces a uniform (random fibre) mat in batch mode (one mat at a time). This lab-scale system provides a cost effective method to fabricate test mats for composite screening, and allows the development of mats with various fibre types, fibre lengths and surface treatments.

The mat forming process is shown schematically in Figure 1. The forming system consists of a large tank with a supported screen and draining system at the bottom. To form fibre mats, natural fibres are first mixed with an aqueous solution to create an evenly distributed fibre slurry. Next, the liquid in the slurry is rapidly drained by opening a large diameter valve/drain at the bottom of the tank. As liquid is removed, a stainless steel screen at the bottom catches the draining fibres to create a round mat (405 mm or 16 inch diameter) of relatively uniform thickness. The round mats are removed and dried in an oven prior to the composite manufacturing stage. This process has been successfully used

to manufacture both short fibre (10 mm or less) and long fibre (>10 mm) mats, although two different methodologies are used. Further details are provided in reference [13].

The lab-scale (wet laid) mat former proved to be a simple and repeatable system. The fibre mats produced with this method showed good uniformity and permeability. Furthermore, this system allows the ability to alter and control the fibre densities of the mats, which is especially important for mixed (hybrid) fibre mats. In addition, the aqueous based system allows for specific fibre treatments to be added during the process.

Figure 1: Lab-scale, wet lay mat forming process: (a) schematic of process, and (b) sample natural fibre mat.

2.3 Composite Manufacturing Methods

Using the (pre-fabricated) non-woven fibre mats, test plates (approximately 40 cm by 40 cm and 2-4 mm thick) were manufactured using the three composite processes: Hand Lay-up (HL), Compression Molding (CM) and Resin Transfer Molding (RTM).

For the hand lay-up composites, chopped strand random glass mats (50 mm long E-glass fibre), dry-laid short fibre mats (Rando-Webber) with 10 mm hemp fibre, dry laid medium fibre mats (Rando-Webber) with 25 mm hemp fibre, and two kinds of dry laid 10 mm flax fibre mats (Rando-Webber) made from retted & whole flax fibre were utilized. Dion 490 polyester resin with 1.5% methylethylketone peroxide (MEKP) initiator was used to make the composites. To achieve different fibre to resin load fractions, multiple layers of fibre mats were used. All hand lay-up samples were fabricated on a flat plate mold, and a roller was used to eliminate entrapped air. All fabricated plates were cured at room temperature for 24 hours, followed by post-curing in an oven at 60°C for 12 hours. Upon removal from the oven and mold, test specimens were machined from the composite plates.

For the compression molded composites, a French press (with temperature/pressure control) with a specially designed plate mold was used. Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) shims were used to control the final thickness of cured plates. The following fibre mats were used in the production of the composites: chopped strand random glass mats (50 mm long E-glass fibre), dry-laid short fibre mats (Rando-Webber) with 10 mm hemp fibre, and wet-laid long fibre mats (in-house mat former) with 50 mm hemp fibre. Envirez T-25 polyester resin with 1.5% MEKP initiator was used as the resin/catalyst system. As in the case of HLU technique, to achieve different fibre to resin load fractions, multiple layers of fibre mats were used.

For the composites produced using resin transfer molding, a laboratory scale RTM machine (MVP Hypaject MK III system from Magnus Venus Plastech) was used to produce the composite plates. The machine consists of the following main units: control unit, resin reservoir/mixing/degassing chamber, and the closed mold. The mold is a specially designed flat mold with clear glass top (used to visualize the resin flow front). Unlike the French press used for compression molding, no lateral pressure is applied to the mold. Sets of the silicone shims were used to match the thickness of the manually compressed fibre mats. For the RTM samples, fibre mats included chopped strand random glass mats (50 mm long E-glass fibre), dry-laid short fibre mats (Rando-Webber) with 10 mm hemp fibre, and

wet-laid long fibre mats (in-house mat former) with 50 mm hemp fibre. Envirez T-25 polyester resin with 1.5% MEKP initiator was used as the resin/catalyst system.

The fibre volume fraction in each composite test plate produced was calculated based on the areal fibre density (*AFD*) in grams per square meter for each composite, average fibre density (ρ_f) in grams per cubic meter, and average plate thickness (d_{plate}) in meters:

$$\text{Fibre volume fraction} = \frac{AFD}{\rho_f \cdot d_{plate}}$$

2.4 Testing Methods

Monotonic tensile tests were conducted as per ASTM D638 using an Instron 4032C load frame (5kN load cell). Tests were conducted under strain control at a rate of 5mm/min. Strain measurements were derived from using both a clip-on extensometer (up to 8% strain) and the cross-head displacement (beyond 8% strain). The tensile modulus was determined from the stress-strain curve using the secant method (between stress levels of 0 and 5MPa), while the tensile strength was taken to be the stress at maximum load. Percent elongation at break was determined as the strain reading at break. In addition to tensile tests, Charpy impact tests were also performed as per ISO 179. All specimens were preconditioned for 48 hours at constant conditions (23°C and 50% relative humidity) prior to testing. A minimum of five specimens were conducted for each tensile and Charpy impact test. In the subsequent plots, the indicated error bars represent the standard deviation of each data point (in the case if such bars are not visible, the standard deviation is too small to be shown at the current plot scale).

3 RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

In this section, the mechanical properties of natural fibre composites based on lay-up and infusion molding methods were investigated. Specifically, three manufacturing methods were examined including hand lay-up, compression molding (CM) and resin transfer molding (RTM). Composite samples were fabricated using natural fibre mats, and the relative performance of the various manufacturing methods were assessed. Comparison was made to glass-fibre composites (baseline).

3.1 Hand Lay-up Results

A series of composite plates were successfully produced using the hand lay-up method. Overall, the hand lay-up technique proved to be challenging when used with natural fibre mats. Natural fibre mats showed good wet-out (resin absorption) properties, however, they were difficult to consolidate due to the nature of the fibres. Unlike straight glass fibres, which form flat mats, the natural fibres are curved and kinked. These fibres resist compression and, therefore, form laminates with significantly larger thickness. Due to the spring-like nature of these mats, they tend to spring back after being compressed by the hand rollers, resulting in an increased number of voids (entrapped air). This resulted in a wide range of measured fibre volume fractions (approx. 4% to 17%).

Figures 2a to 2d summarize the results of the mechanical tests for the hand lay-up samples. It can be seen that the maximum fibre volume fraction achieved by hand lay-up was relative low in all cases (< 18%). The tensile strength of the composites (see Figure 2a) showed a significant difference between the natural and the glass fibre based composites. The E-glass composites demonstrated 4-5 times greater tensile strength at the same fibre volume fractions. In addition, there appears to be no effect of natural fibre length (10 mm versus 25 mm) and natural fibre type (hemp versus flax) for the composite samples tested.

The natural fibre composites manufactured using hand lay-up also had lower strengths than the neat resin (no reinforcement) which is problematic. Again, this can be attributed to the lack of consolidation and air entrapment in these samples (which ultimately weakened the composite), as well as the relatively low fibre volume fractions.

As shown in Figure 2b, the tensile modulus (stiffness) of the natural fibre composites performed

Figure 2: Mechanical properties of composites manufactured using Hand Lay up (HL): (a) tensile strength, (b) tensile modulus, (c) elongation, and (d) Charpy impact toughness.

somewhat better, although the values were still lower than those of the glass-fibre composites (the glass fibre composites yielded a modulus of over 7GPa). Again, no noticeable correlation with the fibre type or length could be observed. These observations hold true for the natural fibre filled composites.

Figure 2c shows the elongation at break for the composites. Composites based on the natural fibres were shown to have a lower elongation than the E-glass composites. Compared to the neat resin, natural fibre based composites show some degradation of the elongation, especially at low fibre volume fraction (such as in the case of hemp medium fibre).

Finally, the Charpy impact strengths (i.e. toughness) for the various composites tested is shown in Figure 2d. The toughness of the natural fibre composites were significantly lower than toughness of the glass-fibre composites. Furthermore, the toughness of the natural fibre composites did not improve significantly compared to the neat resin.

3.2 Compression Molding Results

A series of composite plates were successfully produced using the compression molding (CM) method. Natural fibre mats (dry laid and lab-scale wet laid) were observed to have excellent resin wet-out and good fibre uniformity. Compared to hand lay-up, compression molding tended to produce composite plates with much higher fibre fractions (approx. 19% to 32%) due to the relatively high lateral pressure applied to the composite during the curing stage (the CM technique does not have the same limitation as the hand lay-up procedure, as fibres are constantly subjected to the mold pressure).

Figures 3a to 3d shows a comparison of mechanical properties for both natural and glass fibre composites manufactured using compression molding. Addition of the natural fibres resulted in slight degradation of the tensile strength compared to the neat Envirez resin as demonstrated by Figure 3a. On the other hand, glass fibre composites demonstrated significant improvement of the tensile strength. Hemp fibre composites did not seem to benefit from using long fibre mats: both short and long fibre mat composites demonstrated similar tensile strength. The most likely reason for that was the curved nature of the long fibres. Unlike straight glass fibres, curved hemp fibres cannot transfer the load across the specimen during the tensile test.

Figure 3b shows the tensile modulus (stiffness) of the composites obtained by the CM technique. It can be seen that the natural fibre composites had modulus values approximately 60-80% of the glass-fibre system, which is quite promising. Variation in natural fibre length, however, was shown to have no effect on modulus.

Similar to the composites obtained by the hand lay-up technique, hemp fibre composites manufactured by the CM method resulted in reduced elongation at break as seen from Figure 3c. Glass fibre composites demonstrated slightly better elongation at break. This again can be attributed to the morphological differences between natural and glass fibres.

Similar to the hand laid composites, the toughness of the hemp-fibre composites showed a slight improvement, which increased marginally with increasing fibre volume fraction (see Figure 3d). The glass composites did show a significant improvement compared to both the neat resin and the hemp composites.

3.3 Resin Transfer Molding Results

Finally, a series of composite plates were produced using the resin transfer molding (RTM) technique. Again, natural fibre mats (dry laid and lab-scale wet laid) were observed to have excellent resin wet-out and good fibre uniformity. Similar to compression molding, higher fibre fractions (10% to 25%) were achieved with RTM compared to hand lay-up. While there is no lateral pressure on the RTM mold, the fibre mats are typically compressed when the mold is closed, thus creating higher fibre volume fractions (clamping forces).

The results of the mechanical tests for the RTM composites are shown in Figure 4a to 4d. It can be seen that the properties are similar to results obtained for the compression molded specimens (see Figure 3a to 3d). Again, the natural fibre composites demonstrate a slight strength and elongation reduction compared to the neat resin, with a slight improvement in Charpy toughness. For these properties, the performance of the glass-fibre composites was superior.

Figure 3: Mechanical properties of composites manufactured using Compression Molding (CM): (a) tensile strength, (b) tensile modulus, (c) elongation, and (d) Charpy impact toughness.

Figure 4: Mechanical properties of composites manufactured using Resin Transfer Molding (RTM): (a) tensile strength, (b) tensile modulus, (c) elongation, and (d) Charpy impact toughness.

Similar to compression molded samples, the modulus (stiffness) of the RTM based natural fibre composites was fairly good, and was found to be approximately 60 to 70% of glass fibre systems. The main difference between the RTM and CM composites is the lower volume fractions found in RTM which is due to the fact that there is no continuous lateral pressure on the mold during manufacturing. For both processes, fibre volume fractions were lowest when using long (50 mm) hemp fibre mats fabricated using the lab-scale wet lay process. Due to the tendency of longer fibres to entangle, these mats were observed to have some areas with fibre clumping. As a result, the overall fibre fraction may be lower.

3.4 Comparison Between Various Manufacturing Methods

In general, it can be seen that the properties of the natural fibre composites tested were lower than that for glass-fibre composites for all tests conducted. In addition, there is a clear trend showing an increase in mechanical properties with increasing fibre volume fractions. These trends are quite clear irrespective of manufacturing method. The variability shown in these plots is typical of random fibre composites produced using hand lay-up, compression molding and resin transfer molding.

Overall, the trends for strength, elongation, and toughness of natural fibre composites were found to be much lower than that for the glass-fibre. Furthermore, at lower volume fractions (<20%), the properties of the natural fibre composites were lower than the unreinforced thermoset resins (implying that the addition of natural fibres is actually detrimental).

In terms of modulus (stiffness), natural fibre composites can be seen to approach the glass-fibre systems. For stiffness driven designs, where rigidity is of prime importance, natural fibre composites could provide an attractive alternative to glass-fibre materials, and could be effective as long as minimum values for strength and toughness can be met.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was performed on select specimens to better understanding the effect of morphology on the observed mechanical behaviour. Figures 5 and 6 show the SEM micrographs of the failure surfaces for three composite samples tested: glass fibre, short (10 mm) hemp fibre, and long (50 mm) hemp fibre composites. In Figure 5a, it can be seen that that the glass fibre composite has fibres which are straight and are very uniform in size (diameter and length). Furthermore, as shown in Figure 5b, favourable fibre/resin interfacial strength is demonstrated by residual resin particles bonded to the fibre after failure (pull-out). In contrast, the fibre morphology of short or long hemp fibres is non-uniform and variable (see Figure 6a and 6b, respectively). Unlike straight glass fibres, natural fibres are shown to have various sizes and shapes, and are more prone to curve and kink. This non-uniformity in microstructure ultimately plays a significant role in the reduction in mechanical performance noted above (and in other sections of this report). The lack of interfacial bonding between the resin and fibre can also be seen from these micrographs (very little residual resin on the surface of the fibres after pull out). This is the main driver for improving surface chemistry and characteristics of natural fibres to improve bonding.

Figure 5: Scanning electron micrographs of an E-glass composite test specimen: a) failure surface after mechanical testing, and b) resin residue on E-glass fibre after pull-out.

Figure 6: Scanning electron micrographs of hemp fibre composite test specimens (failure surface after mechanical testing): a) short fibre hemp composite, and b) long fibre hemp composite.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A technical assessment of utilizing natural fibres in thermosetting composites was performed. The following conclusions were derived from this study:

- Natural fibre reinforced thermoset composites were successfully fabricated using a variety of composite manufacturing techniques including hand lay-up, compression molding and resin transfer molding.
- When compared to glass-fibre composites (the current standard), all natural fibre composites tested had lower mechanical properties. Overall, the trends for strength, elongation, and toughness of natural fibre composites were found to be much lower than that for the glass-fibre composites. Furthermore, at lower volume fractions (<20%), these properties for the natural fibre composites were less than the unreinforced thermoset resins, which is somewhat problematic (i.e. this implies that the addition of natural fibre reinforcement is actually detrimental).
- While strength, elongation and toughness properties were poor compared to glass fibre composites, the modulus (stiffness) of natural fibre composites was found to approach that of the glass-fibre systems (up to 70% of the modulus value). For component designs where stiffness or rigidity is of prime importance (e.g. building materials), natural fibre composites could provide an attractive alternative to glass-fibre materials.
- When comparing various composite manufacturing techniques, the hand lay-up method produced natural fibre composites with relatively low volume fractions resulting in poor mechanical properties. This was primarily attributed to a general lack of consolidation and air entrapment in these samples as a result of spring back in the natural fibres (curved and kinked fibres). Glass fibres were observed to have better consolidation and properties due to their uniformity and straightness. Compared to hand lay-up, compression molding and resin transfer molded natural fibre composites tended to have better layer consolidation, higher fibre volume fractions, and improved mechanical performance.
- When comparing various natural fibre types, there was no noticeable difference between the performance of hemp and flax bast fibres. In terms of the effect of fibre length, the test data shows only a slight improvement in mechanical properties using long fibres (50 mm) versus short fibres (10 mm).
- A novel lab-scale, wet laid mat forming system was successfully developed and tested. This system provides a cost effective method to fabricate small-scale, random fibre test mats for composite screening. The system proved to be a simple and repeatable process which

produced fibre mats with variable densities, good uniformity and good permeability characteristics.

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